

EXPERIENCE OF CERTAIN FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN PREVENTING AND COMBATING THE DISSEMINATION OF EXTREMIST IDEAS ON THE INTERNET

Abdulkasimov Mukhammadali Olimjon ugli

Senior Lieutenant in the Active Reserve of Personnel of the Ministry of
Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract: This article examines the experience of certain foreign countries in preventing and countering the spread of extremist ideas on the Internet. It also analyzes the challenges encountered in addressing such types of crimes, contradictions in specific legal provisions, and certain shortcomings in criminal and other relevant legislation. Furthermore, the article provides proposals and recommendations for amendments and additions to national legislation, as well as suggestions regarding the application of legal norms in judicial and investigative practice.

Keywords: Internet, extremism, extremist activity, extremist materials, dissemination, financing, religious extremism, foreign experience, investigative actions.

In recent years, the world community has increasingly encountered the ideological and practical threats of extremism. This disease poses a serious threat not only to individual countries, but also to universal security, sustainable development, and global peace.

Due to the changes taking place in the political, social, and information environment of society on a global scale, the problem of extremism has become even more acute. In particular, the rapid development of information technologies, the popularization of social networks and online platforms have created a favorable environment for those carrying out extremist activities. Today, the Internet has become the main tool for propaganda of extremist and radical content, and its scale of social influence and influence on crime has reached a very high level.

Currently, taking into account the fact that cases of spreading extremist ideas on the Internet are more comprehensive than other crimes, that they can be committed from the territory of one country to the territory of another, that its implementation is economically effective and timely for the perpetrators, and that there are systemic problems with organizational and legal mechanisms in this area, work is being carried out to prevent the spread of extremist ideas on the Internet.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, "Today, all countries of the region are facing threats of terrorism, religious extremism, transnational crime, and drug trafficking. Effective counteraction to these threats can be ensured only jointly, within the framework of practical cooperation mechanisms between the countries of the region. We firmly believe that it is necessary to abandon the division of security threats into "one's own and others'," and to practically adhere to the principle of "integrated security" [1].

In our republic, comprehensive program measures are being consistently implemented to prevent and combat the spread of extremist ideas on the Internet. In particular, by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-6255 dated July 1, 2021, the "National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Combating Extremism and Terrorism for 2021-

2026" was approved. In order to prevent the spread of the ideas of extremism and terrorism, the priority tasks of this Strategy are defined as the promotion of the ideology of patriotism, traditional values and tolerance, preventing the spread of the ideas of extremism and terrorism among minors and youth, protecting the rights of women and strengthening their role in the fight against extremism and terrorism, protecting citizens who have been abroad for a long time from the influence of the ideas of extremism and terrorism, combating the use of the World Wide Web for extremist and terrorist purposes, widely involving civil society institutions and mass media in the fight against extremism and terrorism, improving measures for legal prosecution and prosecution for the commission and financing of extremist and terrorist acts, improving the regulatory framework in the field of combating extremism and terrorism, and implementing international and regional cooperation in this area.

The fight against extremism, which poses a threat to the countries and peoples of the world, has become one of the most pressing tasks of the 21st century. If extremism crosses the borders of one state and takes on an international character, then international coordination of efforts is also required in the fight against it. After all, ensuring the sustainable development of humanity depends on this.

The experience of the CIS countries, the USA, and European countries in preventing and combating the spread of extremist ideas on the Internet deserves attention.

First, let's analyze the activities **of the Russian Federation** in preventing and combating the spread of extremist ideas on the Internet. A number of legislative acts aimed at combating extremism have been adopted by **the legislative bodies of the Russian Federation**, and it would be appropriate to dwell on the main ones.

The main legislative act regulating liability for extremist crimes is the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation. The Criminal Code of the Russian Federation pays great attention to the fight against extremism, and liability is established through several articles directly related to extremism. In particular, Article 280 of the Criminal Code of the Russian Federation [\[3\]](#) establishes criminal liability for "public calls to carry out extremist activities," as well as part 2 of this article "if such actions are committed through the mass media or information and telecommunication networks, including the Internet." Additionally, Article 2821 of this Code establishes criminal liability for "Creating an Extremist Society," Article 2822 for "Organization of Extremist Organization Activities," Article 2823 for "Financing Extremist Activities," and Article 2824 for "Propaganda or public demonstration of Nazi attributes or symbols, attributes or symbols of extremist organizations, repeated propaganda or public demonstration of other attributes or symbols prohibited by federal laws."

In addition, in order to combat extremism in the Russian Federation, the Federal Law of the Russian Federation "On Combating Extremist Activity" was adopted on July 25, 2002. This law regulates the basic concepts of extremism, the basic principles of countering extremist activity, the main directions of countering extremist activity, measures to prevent extremist activity and its prevention, international cooperation in countering extremism, and other similar issues.

This law contains a specific provision, Article 31 of which defines the "Features of the Application of the Legislation of the Russian Federation on Combating Extremist Activity to Religious Texts." It states that the Bible, the Quran, Tanah, and Ganjur, as well as their content and quotations from them, cannot be recognized as extremist material.

Now we will analyze the activities **of the Republic of Kazakhstan**, which borders the Republic of Uzbekistan, in preventing and combating the spread of extremist ideas on the Internet. The main legislative act regulating responsibility for extremist crimes in **the Republic of Kazakhstan** is the Criminal Code **of the Republic of Kazakhstan**. The Criminal Code **of the Republic of Kazakhstan** pays great attention to combating extremism, establishing liability through several articles directly related to extremism. That is, Article 182 of the Criminal Code **of the Republic of Kazakhstan** [5] establishes criminal liability for "Creating, leading, or participating in the activities of an extremist group." In addition, Article 183 "Permission to publish extremist materials in the mass media," Article 258 "Financial support for terrorist or extremist activities and other assistance to terrorism or extremism," Article 259 "Training or arming of persons for the purpose of organizing terrorist or extremist activities," and Article 260 "Pursuing terrorist or extremist training" of this Code establish criminal liability.

Also, in order to combat extremism in the Republic of Kazakhstan, the Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Combating Extremism" was adopted on February 18, 2005. This law regulates the basic concepts of extremism, the basic principles of combating extremism, the main directions of combating extremism, the subjects combating extremism, measures to prevent extremism and its prevention, international cooperation in combating extremism, and other similar situations.

Analyzing the activities **of the Republic of Tajikistan** in preventing and combating the spread of extremist ideas on the Internet, the main legislative act regulating responsibility for extremist crimes in Tajikistan is the Criminal Code **of the Republic of Tajikistan**. The Criminal Code **of the Republic of Tajikistan** pays special attention to combating extremism and establishes liability under several articles directly related to extremism. That is, Article 3071 of the Criminal Code **of the Republic of Tajikistan** establishes criminal liability for "public calls for the implementation of extremist activities and public justification of extremism," as well as part 2 of this article "if such actions are committed using the mass media or the Internet." Furthermore, Article 3072 of this Code establishes criminal liability for "Creating an Extremist Society," Article 3073 for "Organizing the Activities of an Extremist Organization," and Article 3074 for "Creating Educational or Training Groups of a Religious-Extremist Nature."

In addition, in order to combat extremism in the Republic of Tajikistan, the Law of the Republic of Tajikistan "On Combating Extremism"[7] was adopted on January 2, 2020. This law regulates the basic concepts of extremism, the basic principles of combating extremism, the main directions of combating extremism, the subjects of combating extremism, measures to prevent extremism and its prevention, international cooperation in combating extremism, and other similar issues.

We can see that this law defines specific measures to combat extremism. That is, according to Article 22 of the law, the registration of extremist organizations, as well as operational control over persons involved in extremist activities, is carried out by the State Committee for National Security of the Republic of Tajikistan, and the registration of persons prosecuted and (or) convicted of crimes of an extremist nature, as well as persons prosecuted for administrative offenses of an extremist nature, is carried out by the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Tajikistan.

Continuing our analysis, we will examine the activities of the Republic of Belarus in preventing and combating the spread of extremist ideas on the Internet. The main legal document regulating liability for extremist crimes in the Republic of Belarus is the Criminal Code of the Republic of Belarus. The Criminal Code of the Republic of Belarus pays great attention to combating extremism, and liability is established through several articles directly related to extremism. That is, Article 3611 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Belarus [8] establishes criminal liability for "organizing or participating in an extremist organization." In addition, Article 3612 "Financing of Extremist Activity," Article 3614 "Promoting Extremist Activity," and Article 3615 "Training or Other Preparation for Participation in Extremist Activity" of this Code establish criminal liability.

Also, in order to combat extremism in the Republic of Belarus, the Law of the Republic of Belarus "On Combating Extremism" was adopted on January 4, 2007. This law regulates the basic concepts of extremism, the basic principles of combating extremism, the main directions of combating extremism, the subjects of combating extremism, measures to prevent extremism and its prevention, international cooperation in combating extremism, and other similar issues.

Although laws have been adopted and necessary measures are being implemented in Uzbekistan to combat and prevent extremism, the rapid development of the internet, the attempts of various extremist organizations and groups to achieve their malicious goals through the internet, the increasing number of cases of spreading extremist ideas through the internet, and the adoption of laws and measures in the field of preventing and combating extremism require further improvement based on the current situation.

First of all, the role of state bodies carrying out activities to counter extremism is of great importance in preventing and combating extremism. The reason is that they carry out systematic and effective work to combat extremism within the framework of their powers. Article 15 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Extremism" [9] specifies the state bodies carrying out activities to combat extremism. According to it, activities to counter extremism:

- State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Implemented by the Department for Combating Economic Crimes under the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Currently, in our country, a large number of crimes related to extremism are committed using the Internet, the number of such crimes is increasing, as well as the proliferation of materials on social networks containing extremist and similar negative ideas, the timely detection of such materials and their prevention remain the main task. This issue, namely **fighting against the use of the World Wide Web for extremist and terrorist purposes**, is defined as the main priority task in the "National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Combating Extremism and Terrorism for 2021-2026," which also indicates the relevance of the issue.

The Ministry of Digital Technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan is an important state body in solving the above-mentioned urgent issues and implementing the "National Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Combating Extremism and Terrorism for 2021-2026."

However, Article 15 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Extremism" does not include the Ministry of Digital Technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan as an authorized body among the state bodies carrying out activities to combat extremism.

If we consider the Law of some foreign states, including the Republic of Tajikistan "On Combating Extremism," it includes the State Communications Service of the Republic of Tajikistan among the state bodies carrying out activities to counter extremism, whose powers include: monitoring the activities of websites and social networks (internet providers) in order to ensure information security; informing national security agencies and other law enforcement agencies within its competence in the event of detection of materials of an extremist nature; monitoring the activities of social networks and, if necessary, preventing extremist activity. (internet providers) restrict or temporarily suspend their activities, and cooperate with relevant state bodies in the field of countering extremism.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the timely detection and prevention of crimes related to extremism committed through the Internet, as well as materials containing extremist ideas disseminated on social networks on the Internet, remains a pressing issue, and at the same time, taking into account foreign experience, in order to fully use the capabilities of the Ministry of Digital Technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan in preventing the spread of extremist ideas on the Internet, one of the urgent tasks is to include this state body among the authorized state bodies in the fight against extremism.

References:

1. Address by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the international conference "Central Asia: One Past and a Common Future, Cooperation for Sustainable Development and Progress" // www.president.uz - Official website of the Press Service of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
2. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/5491626>
3. https://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_10699
4. <https://docs.cntd.ru/document/901823502>
5. <https://adilet.zan.kz/rus/docs/K1400000226>
continent-online.com/Document/?doc_id=30397325
7. <http://www.portali>
huquqi.tj/publicadliya/view_qonunhovview.php?showdetail=&asosi_id=22828
8. <https://pravo.by/document/?guid=3871&p0=hk9900275>
9. <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/3841957>